

The Fluoremetric Formula.

BY K. S. GURURAJA DOSS,

Desha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1363) has described a new method of analysis of the same order of sensitiveness as colorimetry and nephelometry. He has called it fluoremetry, the property of fluorescence being taken advantage of in the process. This technique will certainly prove highly useful for the determination of minute quantities of a considerable number of substances which are either fluorescent by themselves or can be rendered so by means of suitable reagents.

In his experiments, ultra-violet rays from a mercury arc filtered from most of the visible radiation are used to excite fluorescence in solutions of such substances contained in the comparison cylinders of the Kober-nephelometer. The intensity of fluorescent light thus produced, as observed in the eyepiece of the instrument, is equalised in the usual manner by altering the heights of the columns included in the field of view of the optical plunger.

He finds that for sufficiently dilute solutions the curve obtained by plotting the scale readings against concentration is quite regular. He also says that such a curve corresponds more closely to the curve drawn according to the Kober's nephelometric formula than that of inverse proportionality (colorimetric curve). He also suggests that a further elimination of the errors in the measurement or a further modification of the formula may reduce the lack of agreement.

The Kober's nephelometric formula referred to in the above paper is empirical as is evident from Kober's own words (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1913, **13**, 498): "The readings of the nephelometer plotted against the ratios of solutions for a given standard solution and a given height of the standard, seem to follow a uniform curve which can be expressed in the equation $y = \frac{S}{x} - \frac{S(1-x)k}{x^2}$, where y is the height of the un-

known solution, S , the height of the standard solution, and x , the ratio of solutions. An attempt is made by Wells (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 267) to give a theoretical basis for the Kober's formula; but his theoretical first approximation formula proves to be simpler than Kober's, and the latter is in better agreement with experiment; as Wells himself points out, this reflects on the unknown factors introduced in nephelometry. In the possibly simpler case of fuometry it may be advantageous to derive a theoretical formula and compare it with Kober's, an attempt at which is made in this paper.

Studies on the intensity of fluorescence show that traces of an active substance present in a medium are capable of producing intense fluorescence and if the concentration is increased beyond a few per cent., the brightness is greatly reduced. The existence of the optimum concentration has been explained by Brunninghaus (*Compt. Rend.*, 1909, **149**, 1375) as a result of absorption of light; the increase in concentration though brings about an increase in fluorescence there will be an increase in absorption and the fluorescent intensity is therefore given by an equation of the form $I = Kxe^{-kx}$, where x is the concentration of the fluorescent substance. Though this was in accordance with the measurements made on the cathodo-luminescence of manganese in calcium phosphate it is unable to explain recent experimental work (Merritt, *J. Opt. Soc. Amer.*, 1926, **12**, 613), Perrin (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, **178**, 1405) has tried to explain the same phenomenon on the basis of protective action. Perrin's idea has been successfully made use of by Merritt (*loc. cit.*) to explain quantitatively the variation of fluorescent power with concentration. Recently, Jette and West (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **A**, **121** 299) have suggested an explanation by extending the conception of the collisions of the second kind to the case of solutions. They ascribe the diminishing fluorescent power of a substance with increasing concentration to the collisions of the second kind between the photo-excited and the ordinary fluorescent molecules. It is also to be noted that a "Perrin protection" becomes more or less identical with a collision of the second kind if the former is assumed to take place only at molecular distances. If the life of the excited molecule is long enough, the intensity may also depend on the viscosity of the solution which affects the rate of diffusion and hence the probability of the molecule being within the range of action of another fluorescent molecule, in the duration of

the excited state. The duration of the excited state is found to be very brief in the case of aqueous solutions (Perrin: *Compt. rend.*, 1926, 182, 219).

Let us now apply the above ideas for the derivation of the formula for fluoremetry. Let us assume that if two fluorescent molecules are at a distance apart that is less than a distance ρ , their luminiscence is completely destroyed or greatly reduced. In the case of aqueous solutions where the duration of the critical state is small, if we direct our attention on some molecule, the probability that another molecule will not lie within a sphere of radius ρ is $1 - \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho^3/V$. The probability that all of the other molecules satisfy the condition is $\left(1 - \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho^3/V\right)^n$, where n is the number of molecules in V c.c.

If we put $V=1$, and $n = \frac{cN}{M}$, where c is the concentration in grammes per c.c., M the molecular weight, N the Avogadro number, then the probability expression reduces itself to $e^{-\gamma c}$, where $\gamma =$

$$-\log e \left(1 - \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho^3\right)^{N/M}$$

Now as c is the total concentration, the effective concentration of the fluorescent molecules is $c e^{-\gamma c}$

Let us consider a layer of solution of thickness dy . Let the distance through which the normally incident light must travel through the solution before it can reach the axis of the plunger be Δ . Let the incident intensity be I_0 . Then the intensity of the light exciting the molecule under the field of view of the plunger is $I_0 e^{-(a+bc)\Delta}$ where a and b are the absorption coefficients for the solvent and the solute respectively for the incident radiation. (We assume here the truth of Lambert and Beer's law for fluorescent substances: cf. Kempf, *Physikal. Z.*, 1911, 12, 761; Nichols and Merritt, *Phys. Rev.*, 1910, 31, 500).

Then the fluorescent intensity due to the layer will be

$$\lambda I_0 c^{-(a+bc)\Delta} c e^{-\gamma c} dy$$

where λ is a constant. Applying correction for the absorption of fluorescent light by successive layers we get, the fluorescent intensity due to the layer

$$dI = \lambda I_0 e^{-(a+bc)\Delta} c e^{-\gamma c} e^{-(p+qc)y} dy$$

where p and q are the absorption coefficients for the solvent and solute respectively for the fluorescent radiation. By integration we get the expression for the total intensity which is kept constant in any single set of fluorometric measurements. So, one may write

$$\frac{c e^{-\gamma c} e^{-(a+bc)\Delta} \left\{ e^{-(p+qc)h} - 1 \right\}}{-(p+qc)} = \text{constant.}$$

This is the accurate formula for fluorometry.

But this formula is too complicated for actual use in practice. So let us carry out a few approximations. If we assume that the correction for absorption is small (which is satisfied by dilute solutions) we can use the well-known approximation formula

" $e^x - 1 = xe^{x/2}$ ", and express the above relation in the form

$$ch e^{-\beta c} e^{-\frac{(p+qc)h}{2}} = K_1$$

where β and K_1 are constants. This formula can be directly employed as p and q can be directly measured and the other two constants can be calculated from two measurements of c and h . To simplify the expression further, we can carry out the following approximation:

We can neglect $\frac{ph}{2}$, as the amount of light absorbed by water is small and assume that $\frac{qch}{2}$ is constant in the correction factor as ch is fairly constant owing to the smallness of the absorptive and protective effects. Then we get

$$ch e^{-\beta c} = K_2$$

Let us now study the relationship of this formula to the usual empirical formulæ used in nephelometry.

As the absorption and protection effects are of a small order we can put $c = \frac{k}{h}$ in the correction factor. Thus we get

$$ch e^{-ak/h} = \text{constant.}$$

Or we can write

$$c_1 h_1 e^{-ak/h} = c_2 h_2 e^{-ak/h}$$

or

$$\frac{c_1}{c_2} = \frac{h_2}{h_1} \left\{ 1 + ak \left(\frac{1}{h_1} - \frac{1}{h_2} \right) \right\}$$

to a first approximation. If h_2 is the standard height we can put $\frac{ak}{h_2} = -\delta$ and hence,

$$\frac{c_1}{c_2} = \frac{h_2}{h_1} \left\{ 1 + \delta \left(1 - \frac{h_2}{h_1} \right) \right\}.$$

This formula is identical with Wells' empirical formulæ for nephelometry, which has been tested and found to be in agreement with Kober's data (Wells; *loc. cit.*). This is more convenient for use especially for the slide rule. Also it is to be pointed out that it is so closely approximated a form of the original formula that we get values never differing by more than 0.1% when calculated on the basis of either formulæ.

Now let us proceed in another direction. Again,

$$c_1 h_1 e^{-\beta c_1} = c_2 h_2 e^{-\beta c_2}.$$

$$\frac{h_1}{h_2} = \frac{c_2}{c_1} \left\{ 1 + \beta c_1 \left(1 - \frac{c_2}{c_1} \right) \right\}$$

to a first approximation. This is of the same form as the Kober's formula:

$$\frac{h_1}{h_2} = \frac{c_2}{c_1} \left\{ 1 + k \left(1 - \frac{c_2}{c_1} \right) \right\}$$

and the two can be equated if c_1 is constant, *i.e.*, if it is the concentration of the standard solution. But Kober takes c_2 as the standard and so far the theoretical formula differs from Kober's.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

Let us now consider the available experimental data. Apart from the indirect support offered by the Kober's nephelometric data, the theoretical formula in the Wells form seems to be in fair agreement with Desha's fluoremetric data on iodeosine solutions, the maximum difference between theory and experiment being about 1% (see Table II and Fig. 2). But the data on quinine sulphate solutions show a large deviation, the maximum amounting to about 4% (See Table I and Fig. 1).

Lastly let us examine the shape of the " $ch-c$ " curve as obtained from Desha's experimental data. As c is a continuous function of h , we must expect the " $ch-c$ " curve to be continuous. The mean smooth experimental curve is found to be convex towards the Y-axis. This is an extremely interesting observation if we could absolutely depend on Desha's results. For, whereas the accurate theoretical formula must give a curve concave to the Y-axis even at fairly high concentrations, we find just the reverse to be the case in practice. This discrepancy between the theoretical and the experimental values seems to be of profound significance from the point of view of the theory of fluorescence in general and the theories of inhibition of fluorescence in particular. I would not like to attempt at any quantitative derivation to account for the difference, as I feel that some more experimental work is necessary to consider this as but a sure and general tendency.

TABLE I.

Quinine sulphate solutions.

<i>c.</i>	<i>h</i> (exp.).	<i>h</i> (theor.).	<i>ch</i> (exp.).	<i>ch</i> (theor.).
2.0	10.28	10.28	20.56	20.56
1.7	11.98	11.80	20.37	20.06
1.4	14.53	14.00	20.34	19.60
1.3	16.76	16.08	20.11	19.30
1.0	19.50	19.00	19.50	19.00
0.8	24.10	23.40	19.28	18.72
0.6	31.15	30.73	18.69	18.44
0.5	36.60	36.60	18.30	18.30

TABLE II.

Iodeosine solutions.

<i>c.</i>	<i>h</i> (exp.).	<i>h</i> (theor.).	<i>ch</i> (exp.).	<i>ch</i> (theor.).
4.0	16.00	16.00	64.00	64.00
3.5	17.83	17.65	64.19	63.54
3.2	19.90	19.72	63.68	63.10
2.6	24.25	24.02	63.05	62.45
2.0	30.90	30.90	61.80	61.80

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